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Current Applications of Suzuki–Miyaura Coupling Reaction in The Total Synthesis of Natural Products: An update

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Abstract

Suzuki-Miyaura Coupling Reaction (SMCR) has been extensively used in the total synthesis of natural products. We underscored these achievements in a report published in *Tetrahedron* up to 2012. Since then, there has been tremendous growth in this field and numerous articles have been published after 2012. In this review, we tried to go insight and highlight the current developments in the applications of SMCR as a key and strategic step (steps) in the total synthesis of biologically active natural products accomplished and reported from 2012 till date.

Keywords: carbon-carbon bond formation, Natural products, Palladium, Suzuki-Miyaura reaction, Total synthesis